

On the Tensile Strength of Jute-fibre.

BY POLIN BEHARI SARKAR.

The fundamental defects for which jute is comparatively less important commercially are mainly its lack of durability and high lignin content. It is a well known fact that when exposed to dampness, the fibre loses much of its strength, the decaying process is supposed to be bacterial. Which component of the fibre is more susceptible to the attack of bacteria and how the process of deterioration goes on, are still unknown. In any case, this decomposition of the fibre has to be prevented in order to make it more useful for commercial purposes. Secondly, the presence of lignin makes the fibre tough and practically unfit for spinning. The light yellow colour due to lignin cannot be bleached by ordinary means. Thus lignin must be completely removed before it can be employed as a textile fibre just like cotton. But unfortunately all strength is lost with delignification, when the fibre is moist. Hence the removal of lignin while maintaining its strength is the real problem.

An attempt has been made here to study the factors on which the strength of the fibre actually depends, the conditions under which the deterioration takes place, as well as the effects of various chemical treatments on the tensile strength of the fibre before and after delignification. The tensile strength has been measured in an apparatus specially designed for the purpose. This consists of an ordinary balance in which the left pan has been replaced by two clips A and B. (A) is suspended from the left beam while (B) is attached to the balance pillar and can be moved up and down by rack and pinion arrangement (C). The right-hand beam carries a chain (D) the free end of which is attached to a sliding clip (E) which is provided with a pointer and can be moved along a vertical glass rod (F). The chain helps to make delicate adjustments without causing any jerk. The weights thus added can be calculated from the scale (G) provided it is previously calibrated. The arrangement is shown below,

A. Upper clip. B. Lower clip. C. Rack and pinion arrangement. D. Chain. E. Sliding clip. F. Vertical glass rod. G. Scale. H. Pointer on sliding clip.

The fibre is rarely uniform in the true sense of the term, the diameter is never the same all through. The breaking weight being essentially dependent on the cross sectional area of the fibre, tensile strength was always measured with a fairly uniform fibre. The diameter was determined with a travelling microscope at different parts of the fibre and the mean was taken. At the same point however, the diameter is not always the same, the cross section being elliptical. So several readings were taken for the diameter at each point after turning the fibre, the mean giving the diameter of the fibre at that point. To avoid error in sampling only one or two fibres were selected from each stalk. The balance was adjusted by keeping the attached chain fixed at the lowest point. After carefully tightening the fibre, at both ends by A and B, C was very slowly turned to stress the fibre properly so that on releasing the pan the pointer remained at the zero position. The tightening of the fibre requires the greatest skill, if it be too tight at either end the fibre breaks there evidently with a lesser weight. When this took place the reading was discarded.

The weights must be very gradually increased, for it has been observed that a fibre not breaking with a greater weight, breaks with a smaller one if the latter be placed all at once. Several readings were taken with the same fibre and the mean accepted as the breaking weight. It has been noticed that with a certain weight the fibre does not break as soon as the pan is raised but only after a few seconds. Even with all possible precautions the results were seldom coincident. Twenty five, observations were therefore taken in each case, the mean representing the tensile strength. In the same sample a few fibres were found to be abnormally strong, while a few others subnormally weak; these were discarded while taking the mean. The tensile strength was calculated from the formula:—

$$T = \frac{W}{\pi(d/2)^2}$$

The weight w was expressed in kg. and the diameter in mm.

Deterioration of Jute-fibre with Time.

In order to see how the fibre deteriorates with time, the tensile strength of a two years old sample of jute kept in a cupboard was measured. Green jute plant was retted in the laboratory and the tensile strength of the fresh fibre obtained therefrom was then determined. The difference was inappreciable. Thus the statement "even under ordinary conditions the (jute) fibre becomes brittle and loses much of its strength" (Mathews, "Textile Fibres," 1924, p. 768) is not substantially correct. When exposed to dampness the case is of course different. Unlike cotton, jute fibre showed a slight decrease in tensile strength with increasing humidity and *vice versa*. The results are shown in Table I.

TABLE I.

Specification of jute.	Moisture.	Mean tensile strength.	Standard error.
(a) Fresh fibre obtained by retting, air-dried.	14.80 %	15.61 kg./sq.mm.	± 1.50
(b) Raw jute kept for two years in the cupboard.	14.20	14.46	± 1.46
(c) Sample (b) dehydrated in a drying pistol over P ₂ O ₅ in vacuum.	Nil	18.24	± 1.49
(d) Sample (b) kept under distilled water for 48 hours	...	12.81	± 1.51

Influence of Different Constituents on the Strength of the Fibre.

The influence of the different constituents on the tensile strength was next studied. Fatty and resinous matter was removed by extraction with a boiling mixture of alcohol and benzene (1:1) in a Soxhlet apparatus for 5 to 6 hours. The two years old sample was always taken for investigation. The tensile strength remained practically unchanged after the removal of fats and resins. Lignin was removed completely by chlorine peroxide gas in presence of moisture. The milk-white fibre dissolved to a colourless solution in 72% H_2SO_4 in the cold. The delignified fibre retained its physical structure as seen under the microscope. The tensile strength in the air-dried condition was very nearly the same. This unmistakably indicates that in jute, lignin is not chemically combined with cellulose, otherwise these important physical properties of the fibre would have changed. This has also been observed by Chowdhury and Paul (unpublished paper) in the case of cocoanut fibre. Wislicenus (*Z. Chem. und Kolloid*, 1910, 8, 17, 87), König (*Chem. Z.*, 1912, 36, 1101) and Lehne and Shepman (*Z. angew. Chem.*, 1925, 38, 93) from the study of other lignocellulose also arrived at the same conclusion. The delignified fibre is very flexible and soft to the touch. But unfortunately, the tensile strength while moist, is almost nil—it breaks with any weight however small if the fibre be kept moist with a brush during measurement. Otherwise it dries partly and a moderate value for tensile strength is obtained. Hemicelluloses therefore appear to be the real binding material and not lignin as is usually supposed. Lignin serves more or less as a protective coating. Pectin was then removed from the delignified jute by extraction with 0.5% solution of ammonium oxalate at 80°-90° exhaustively. The tensile strength was found to be a bit lower. The samples were all air-dried and measurements were made in the same week, so the moisture content was not determined. Table II gives the experimental results.

TABLE II.

Specification of jute.	Mean tensile strength.	Standard error.
(a) Raw jute after removal of resin and fat	14.30	± 1.50
(b) Delignified jute, air-dried	15.32	± 1.48
(c) Do moist	10.86	± 2.0
(d) Do moistened with a brush during measurement	Nil	—
(e) Delignified jute after removal of pectin	14.72	± 1.38

Influence of Dampness on Jute-fibre.

The rate at which the fibre loses its strength when exposed to dampness was then determined. Raw jute was kept under tank water in a porcelain vessel and tensile strength was measured from time to time. It will be seen from Table III that the deterioration is not so rapid as is usually observed when the fibre is in contact with the soil. This might be due to the action of bacteria coming therefrom as well as the nitrogenous matter present therein. The colour became darker with time and the fibre harsh to the touch. It is interesting to note here that the portion of the fibre above the water surface was very much weaker (as tested by the hand) than that under water.

TABLE III.

Sample—Raw jute.

Time.	Mean tensile strength.	Standard error.	Colour.
Nil	14.46	± 1.46	Very pale brown
30 days	13.58	± 1.47	" "
60	12.16	± 1.48	Light grey
90	11.31	± 1.47	" "
120	10.67	± 1.49	Grey
150	10.02	± 1.51	Dark grey

Prevention of Deterioration of Fibre.

In order to prevent the deterioration of the fibre it was treated in the cold with a 40 % solution of formaldehyde for 48 hours. The fibre was thoroughly washed, dried in air and its tensile strength measured. The value was, however, found to be almost double the original. With delignified fibre as well, the same rise was observed, but not in the moist condition. Jute was treated with cold and dilute NaOH for the same period, the tensile strength increased much in this case also. Alkaline formaldehyde was more efficient than acid solution in improving the tensile strength. Phenol and formaldehyde had the same influence as formaldehyde alone. The colour turned brown after alkali treatment, but remained unchanged

in acid and neutral formaldehyde treatment. In the former case the fibre became softer. In the case of mixed treatment the ratio was always 1:1.

TABLE IV.

Treatment.	Mean tensile strength.	Standard error.	Colour.	
			Light	brown.
(1) Raw jute (air-dried)	14.46	± 1.46	„	„
(2) Do with 40% H·CHO	26.37	—	„	„
(3) „ „ 10% „	25.46	—	„	„
(4) „ „ 10% CH ₃ COOH	13.62	—	„	„
(5) „ „ 8% NaOH	33.17	± 1.61	Pale	brown
(6) „ „ 1% NaOH	33.77	—	„	„
(7) „ „ 10% acetic acid and 10% formaldehyde	31.39	—	Unchanged	
(8) With 4% NaOH and 10% H·CHO	42.0	± 2.08	Brown	
(9) „ 1% NaOH and 10% H·CHO	40.43	—	„	
(10) 10% H·CHO and 10% phenol	27.0	± 1.92	Unchanged	
(11) „ 10% H·CHO and normal H ₂ SO ₄	23.80	—	„	
(12) Delignified jute	15.32	—	White	
(13) Do with 10% H·CHO	26.46	± 2.10	„	
(14) „ 10% H·CHO and 1% NaOH	40.15	—	Pale	yellow
(15) „ 1% NaOH alone	32.80	± 1.93	„	„

Bacterial Decomposition of Jute-fibre.

Bacterial decomposition of jute, both treated and untreated was next studied. Green jute plant was retted in a porcelain vessel and the fibre under examination was dipped in it. The bacteria present in the over-retted jute hastened the process of deterioration. It is interesting to note here that in a galvanised iron vessel jute did not ret even in three months in stagnant water. Metallic zinc has therefore a distinct inhibiting action on the retting of jute. The tensile strength was measured every week. From the results given in Table V it is evident that raw jute is more resistant than delignified jute, showing thereby the protective nature of lignin.

Formaldehyde treated jute (raw) practically withstands all bacterial attack while delignified jute similarly treated undergoes slight deterioration. Formaldehyde, therefore, can be employed as a valuable bactericide in the case of jute to increase its durability.

TABLE V.
Mean tensile strength of

Time.	Raw jute.	Raw jute and H'CHO.	Delignified jute.	Delignified jute and H'CHO.
Nil.	14.46	26.37	15.32	26.45
7 days	14.02	26.08	13.75	26.06
14	13.68	26.03	12.76	25.66
21	13.00	26.01	11.60	25.40
28	12.46	25.80	10.52	25.00
35	11.71	25.53	9.45	24.67
42	11.00	25.52	8.50	24.08
49	10.02	25.00	7.00	23.80
56	9.30	24.87	5.70	23.32
63	9.00	24.80	4.34	22.88

All attempts to maintain the strength of the delignified fibre in the moist condition have so far proved futile. Formaldehyde alone and with various other chemicals were found to be ineffective. Further work in this direction is in progress.

SUMMARY.

1. The tensile strength of jute fibre after various treatments has been measured by an apparatus specially designed for the purpose.

2. With increasing moisture the tensile strength diminishes and *vice versa*.

3. Deterioration with time is very negligible if the jute be kept in a dry place.

4. The maintenance of strength and structure by delignified jute supports the view that in jute, lignin and cellulose are not chemically combined.

5. Formaldehyde increases the tensile strength of the fibre specially in slightly alkaline solution. It also prevents the bacterial decomposition of both raw and delignified fibre.

6. Removal of lignin makes the fibre more susceptible to bacterial action.

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Vitamin C in Indian Food-stuffs.

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Since the identification of vitamin C (ascorbic acid) with "Hexuronic acid" additional interest has naturally been aroused in obtaining further information about it. The reducing property of ascorbic acid has been taken advantage of for the determination of the ascorbic acid content of different materials, both of vegetable and animal origins. The Tillmans technique of titration with the oxidation-reduction indicator, 2:6-dichlorophenol-indophenol, has been modified by Harris and Ray (*Biochem. J.*, 1933, 27, 303) and Birch, Harris and Ray (*ibid.*, 1933, 27, 590) and they claim that in general the figures obtained by the chemical method agree with those obtained by the biological technique of assay.

The present paper records certain results obtained by the titration technique with the extracts of some Indian food-stuffs and it will be observed that some of the fruits investigated have a very high reducing power. The vitamin C content of germinated and ungerminated mung (*Phaseolus mungo*) has been investigated by both the chemical and biological methods.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Titration with 2:6-dichlorophenol-indophenol.—Essentially the method of Harris and Ray (*loc. cit.*), and Birch, Harris and Ray